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THE FRAM STRAIT TOMOGRAPHY EXPERIMENT 2008

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NERSC Technical report No. 298

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Executive summary.

Two field experiments have been carried out in connection with the tomography experiment in the Fram Strait.

In the first Cruise, during 14-18 August 2008, the acoustic tomography system was successfully deployed from RV Håkon Mosby. In addition we deployed 7 transponders, a McLane profiling CTD mooring near the tomographic source mooring, and 9 CTD stations were taken between the source and the receiver mooring.

During the second cruise 19-26 September 2008 using the KV Svalbard it was confirmed that the tomography system is working, 20 acoustic listening stations were obtained, 16 XBTs were obtained along the acoustic track, AWIs sea glider was recovered, UPMC Moored Ocean Profiler (MOP) mooring and AWI winch mooring were recovered, and finally 3 ice stations were visited.

The two cruises were successfully carried out with the exception that we were not able to download the acoustic data using acoustic modems.

As part of the "Bridge building" project between NERSC-WHOI-SIO, funded by the Norwegian Research Council, Peter Worcester from SIO and Andrey Morozov from WHOI were visiting Svalbard and Bergen for testing, preparation and participating in field experiment. To ensure exchange of expertise and competence building young scientists, experienced scientists and representatives from companies participated in the two cruises. After the RV Håkon Mosby cruise, a workshop was held at NERSC where Peter Worcester and Andrey Morozov gave lectures.

This technical report is entirely based on the DAMOLCES deliverable D8.2-05: Tomography experiment 2008.

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Acoustic tomography experiment in the Fram Strait

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Cruise report

Acoustic tomography experiment in the Fram Strait

RV Håkon Mosby 14-18 August 2008

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Introduction

As part of the DAMOCLES Integrated Project (Developing Arctic Modeling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies), a first step acoustic tomography system was successfully installed in the Fram Strait in August 2008 using R/V Håkon Mosby. A first attempt to deploy the tomography system was done in October 2007, however the deployment was interrupted due to strong winds and heavy sea.

The deployment cruise in 2008 was preceded by a couple of months of careful testing at laboratory at the Geophysical Institute, at the University of Bergen, and one week of preparation work in Longyearbyen. Upgrading and testing of experiment schedules was carried out in Bergen. Final assembly, checkout of the instruments and placing experiment schedules in instrument flash memory was carried out in the Lab at UNIS in Longyearbyen. During the four day long cruise with RV Håkon Mosby two tomographic moorings, 7 acoustic transponders and a MMP mooring (IOPAN) was successfully deployed. In addition an oceanographic section, consisting of 9 CTD stations, was obtained between the source and the receiver.

This report, provide an overview the specific objectives of the tasks to be carried out during the experiment, details of the different tasks are described in separate sections, and finally a summary of preliminary results obtained during the experiment.

The experiment objectives.

The objectives of the deployment cruise were to:

1. Carry out laboratory tests and pre-launch tests of the instruments for the two tomographic moorings (Resp:NERSC)
2. Deploy two tomographic moorings in the Fram strait according to the design developed during the DAMOCLES integrated project. (Resp. NERSC)
3. Prepare and test the acoustic modems mounted on the tomographic mooring. (Resp. Aquatec)
4. Deploy the McLane profiler mooring (IOPAN) at safe distance from the source mooring in 1500 m deep water.(Resp. IOPAN)
5. Obtain CTD section and bathymetry between source and receiver. Bathymetry and GPS (position and time) is automatically logged in the ship data logging system.(Resp. NERSC)

Prior to the deployment cruise a detailed plan was prepared to meet the major objectives. The cruise plan was distributed to the participants and to the ship.

Checkout and preparation

After the cancelled deployment in October last year the acoustic instruments was transported back to Bergen, and stored from the end of December 2007 to the end of April 2008 in NAXYS warehouse. A container was bought 20 April to ease the logistics in Bergen and later in Longyearbyen.

Two phases of check out and testing was carried out. First phase, upgrades, and laboratory tests of the STARS and STAR/WRC were carried out May/June/July in the Laboratory at the Geophysical Institute. The work was performed by NERSC personnel in close e-mail contact with SIO and Webb

Research Corporation. The pre-launch testing carried at UNIS, Longyearbyen by NERSC personnel together with Peter Worcester (SIO) and Andrey Morozow.

STAR

Testing in Bergen

During testing in Bergen (May-June-mid July) all equipment was kept in the container stationed at Geophysical Institute, Marineholmen, Bergen. The two STARS, SN10 and SN11 were first upgraded before laboratory tests could start. The upgrade consisted of changing and upgrade of software. Thereafter, time was spent on a training process how to operate the system correctly and to detect errors.

First problem we had was to achieve the GPS signal to set the clock in the deck unit. The GPS signal was very hard to achieve. We realized that the GPS antenna between the UiB buildings was not the optimal place as we then were in a shadow zone for the signals from the satellite. After some days, we found out the while the signal was bad before lunch it was much better after 12:30 (local time).

Second problem was that the hydrophone on blue cable on Array-2 was unstable. The hydrophone was exchanged with a new hydrophone under warranty.

Third problem occurred when we checked the results of overnight tests as we realized that there was no data or engineering files found on the hard disk. Changing from "save processed data" to 'Realtime output processing' solved this. Furthermore, to be on the safe side, we decided to keep to STAR native file format and not using the more recently implemented Netcdf format.

Fourth problem was an error in the creation date of the files. This was solved by doing a complete initializing of the disks and to set the time before the initialization to get the correct time on the creating data of the files.

Fifth was an indication of a problem with SN 11. During test runs of experiments not all acoustic reception data were written to file. The error is referred to with 'rev resid' in the log file, and indicates that not all the expected sampling data was transferred from the DSP to the TB486. This seems to be occurring at a higher rate in SN11 than on other STAR instruments. This problem were not solved. SN10 do not have this sporadic error.

Both SN10 and SN11 were initialized and experiment schedule was put into flash memory before leaving Bergen. O-rings were cleaned, but tubes was not evacuated. All batteries for SN 10/11 were tested and found OK.

Testing in Longyearbyen

Also in Longyearbyen we had some problems in achieving GPS signal, but we finally got the best location for the antenna just outside the laboratory at UNIS.

SN 10 was in good shape in the first technical tests. Still some errors in the date of the files generated. This is however no problem, as long as year of day and clock is correct.

SN 11 still has the sporadic failure in writing the acoustic receptions to file. Fails in up to 50% of the receptions, best rate was 1 out of 6 reception fails. Several approaches were made to solve the problem. It was discussed if we should or not should deploy it, we decided to deploy it any way.

O-rings were cleaned and both tubes were evacuated 13 August. Time checks were carried out during the day using PPP and pressure in the tubes are tested several times during the day. Moved the STARS

to ship early morning 14 August 2008. Photos from the checkout in Bergen and in Longyearbyen can be seen in Figure 1.

In May, June and July 2008 test and check-out of the STARS were carried out by Svein Arild, Johan and Hanne.

After transportation to UNIS, Longyearbyen all the instrument was tested running through the Prelaunch test scheme provided by SCRIPPS.

Supervision and discussions with Peter Worcester was very much appreciated.

Steinar Myking and Andrey inspect one of the STAR battery units. Electronic (left) unit and batteries (right). Hydrophone cable to the right in the photo.

Johan and Kjersti were cleaning the STARs carefully.

Before batteries and electronic unit were put into the tubes. Here batteries are inserted into the tube by Stein and Johan.

Figure 1. Testing and preparation of the acoustic receivers.

Tomography Source.

Testing in Bergen

STAR (SN14)/WRC was upgraded similar to the two standalone STARs. After the upgrade the STAR controller was checked in overnight runs. It was found navigation and receive errors. The FPIC was replaced by a spare FPIC and the problems were gone. To test the integration of the STAR controller unit with the Webb source a dummy load experiment was carried out. Source was run for 3+4 days with 4 hourly transmissions every hour without any hanging. Hanging means that the source goes into a semi sleeping mode where it do not transmit any more as the STAR can not contact it, but this did never happen in our tests. Dummy load experiment components and set up is shown in Figure 2. Prior to transportation to Longyearbyen an experiment schedule was loaded into flash memory.

Testing in Longyearbyen.

In Longyearbyen the source was tested according to the Pre-launch schedule provided by SCRIPPS. Source testing in Longyearbyen is illustrated in Figure 3, 7-14 August 2008. Full source test with 20% power was successfully carried out. Since no deep water test prior to deployment was possible Andrey Morozov run extra tests to check the electronics and connectors.

Finally, source electronics was installed into the tube. A difficulty with using the PPP occurred, and it was decided to use the Ethernet connection, meaning that the vacuum is broken. Correspondingly, the source had to be evacuated just before deployment onboard the ship. Moved to ship early morning 14 August 2008.

Acoustic modem.

Bergen.

June 8-11 2008, Aquatec personnel visited Bergen, and the modems were tested and upgraded with new software. Tests were carried out by separating the modems horizontally by 2 km using test site at NAXYS and NUI in Bergen. However, no contact with modems were established most likely due to very noisy ocean (heavy waves, rainy and ship traffic).

A second test was carried out, by NERSC personnel, in the Puddefjord harbor from one pier to another. The modems were separated approximately 300 m from each other. The two modems replied to the interrogation, and we were able to receive 1-2 blocks of data. The ambient noise level in this region is relatively high and the water is very shallow so the result might not be too bad. Downloaded files were sent to Aquatec for further analysis. However, at this point the download of data did not seem easy, so it was decided that Aquatec should join the cruise with RV Håkon Mosby to ensure optimal handling of the acoustic modems.

Longyearbyen.

In Longyearbyen the acoustic modems were upgraded with respect to software, and several tests was carried out in the Laboratory. It is always difficult to do acoustic dry tests with instruments made for underwater communication.

Modems were mounted at the STARs and the source by use of clamps prior to transportation to the ship.

Swapping the FPIC in SN14.

Star deck cable connected to the SN 14

Electronic Endcap of the source.

SAIL – Connected to the INSTEK power supply to provide current to the source through the Deck cable

Figure 2. Testing the source in Bergen. The STAR unit was first tested then the STAR / WRC source s was jointly tested in a dummy load experiment (see the drawing). “Wall” in the experiment set up drawing means “safety ground”.

Source was brought into the Laboratory by the fork-truck.

Source electronics on the bench for check-out.

Careful check out of the “mechanical” status of the electronics. After testing the electronics was put into the glass tube again. Dry air was pumped into the tube after mounting.

Electronics installed into the source, and Svein Arild completes the endcap under supervision from Andrey.

Source ready for final full test to check that the sleeves moves and source transmits according to schedule. Source is connected to STAR unit through STAR deck cable, Source power supply through source deck cable, and communication is established through Ethernet.

Source and STARs all have the acoustic modems mounted on their cages and they are all ready to go to the ship.

Figure 3. Testing and preparation of source in Longyearbyen.

Figure 4. Upper photos shows testing of the acoustic modem in Puddefjorden, Bergen by NERSC and UIB personnel. The modem was attached to one of the STAR cages and lowered into the sea outside the pier by a fork-truck. The deck mode was thereafter taken to the other side of the fjord. Interrogation signals was sent several times and the modem replied and sent data back. Only one modem was tested this way.

Lower left shows Carla testing the modems in Longyearbyen.

Deployment of tomography moorings.

Originally the source was planned to be deployed at 78 50 N 7 E, however the sea ice was covering the planned receiver location at 78 50 N 1 E. On 13 August the new deployment sites were decided based on available ice maps and bathymetric information. To avoid sea ice and shallow water regions the two moorings were moved south eastward to roughly 78 30 N and between 2E -8 E. To avoid recalculations and redesign of the source mooring we looked for a site, which had a water depth close to the planned depth of 1469 m. Source mooring design is shown in Figure 5. From the ship navigation system a rough position for the source mooring was selected at 78 30 N 8 22.1 E. Since the ship bathy-maps are in general not very good in these areas we carried out a bathymetric survey to find the exact position to deploy the source. Thereafter, for the receiver mooring we looked for a suitable position, which was close to the planned separation distance 129.7 km, and with a water depth close to the planned depth of 2475 m.

Deployment of source mooring.

RV Håkon Mosby was departing Longyearbyen at 15:00 (Z). At midnight (crossing over to 15 August 2008) we were close to planned source position. A bathymetry survey was carried out immediately,

and based on this a target position was found: 78 30.003 N 8 18.898 E with the water depth very close to 1469m.

Thereafter at 04:40 (Z) a test of acoustic releases (41762/41764) started by lowering them down to 1000m and letting them soak for 30 minutes. Both releases replied and confirmed to be released.

Source was cleaned and evacuated at 7:08 (Z), see figure 6. Deployment started by launching the steel sphere at 8:25(Z) at 78 31.83 8 07.55 E and the source was launched just after at 8:33(Z). Ship was moving with a speed between 1-2 knot. Due to too long distance to target position (we did not want to risk go to far with the mooring hanging behind the vessel) we decided to deploy in slightly shallower water than first planned. The mooring was shortened by 14.4 m. Deployment was completed by dropping the anchor at 10:04 (Z) at 78 30.55 N 8 15:68 E at 1458 water depth 1.18 nm away from the planned target. Between 12:10-12:40 a survey was made to position the anchor (acoustic releases) using three points with 3-5 pings at each location. New anchor position was found to be 78 30.6333 N 8 15.0943 E with water depth 1457 m.

Figure 5. The source mooring design. Steel sphere at the top of the mooring and 16 Benthos glass balls provide the required floatation. Mooring is designed so that the source will be at 400 m under the surface given that the depth is 1469 m.

The STAR serial number SN 14

Modem to be used at this mooring is 852-007

AROGOS beacon: SM500 74604

Releases are:

41762: Release code B/Enable code B/Interrogation frequency 9 kHz/Reply frequency is 10 kHz/48 hours timeout

41764: Release code B/Enable code G/Interrogation frequency 8.5 kHz/Reply frequency is 9.5 kHz/48 hours timeout.

Andrey and Peter cleaning...

and evacuating the source before deployment.

Jac Nil wire attached to the source.

Steel sphere and first cluster of glass balls deployed (8:25 (Z)). Just before deploying the source.

Source is gone into sea at 8:32(Z)

Anchor is lowered and mission is completed 10:04 (Z).

Figure 6. Source Pre-launch testing in Longyearbyen 7-13 August 2008 and deployment 15 August 2008

Four transponders was prepared and checked on deck prior to deployment (Figure 7). Deployment of transponders started 14:00 (Z), and all four transponders were successfully deployed at 15:00 (Z). Thereafter, a survey to position the transponders was carried out. Overview of the deployment positions and result of pinging the transponders are found Table 1 a,b. An overview map of pings and transponder positions are found in Figure 8.

After completion of the transponder survey a final check of the source mooring was carried out. The source is now in monitor schedule, which mean that it will now transmit every hour for 24 hours. At 19:00 (Z) we heard a clear interrogation ping and several replies. At 19:10 (Z) we recorded the first transmission from the source, which lasted for exactly 60 s. Also at 20:00 (Z) and 21:00(Z) the system was functioning perfectly.

Left the source mooring position at 21:30 (Z).

Figure 7. To the left preparation of transponders and bookkeeping. Deployment of the transponder (yellow) and the anchor.

Enter initial position of the target

Latitude deg minutes N S

Longitude deg minutes W E

Depth (m)

Number of Surveys

Push EDIT and enter your survey positions with this format:
 Lat(deg) Lat(min) lon(deg) lon(min) travel_time (secs)

1-way 2-way

Ave. Soundspeed (m/s) Transponder depth (m)

Calculated lat,lon position is:

lat N: 78 deg 30.6333 min

lon E: 8 deg 15.0943 min

Figure 8a. After the deployment of the Anchor at 78 30.55 N 8 15:68 E. A ship survey was carried to ping the acoustic releases to estimate the anchor position. New anchor position was calculated (by Matlab program obtained from Arthur Newhall) to be 78 30.633 N 8 15.0943 E, and the corresponding depth was estimated to be (1453 + 5) m.

Figure 8b. Red crosses marks the drop position of transponders around the source mooring which is indicated by a asterix in blue. Green dots show the positions of the pings carried out from RV Håkon Mosby.

Table 1.a Transponders deployed roughly 1000 m from the drop position.

Transponder-ID	Release code	X-mit freq	RCV freq	Deploy	GMT time	Drop Position-GPS	Depth
TR6001/41927	C	11.0 kHz	9.0 KHz	North	14:14	78 31.085 N 8 15.491 E	1401
TR6001/41923	D	11.5 kHz	9.0 KHz	East	14:27	78 30.534 N 8 18.237 E	1424
TR6001/41913	E	12.0 kHz	9.0 KHz	South	14.35	78 30 N 8 15.5 E	1517
TR6001/41919	F	11.5 kHz	9.0 KHz	West	14:42	78 30.54 N 8 12.7 E	1500

Table 1.b Interrogation of transponders at the source location from RV Håkon Mosby.

Position (N)	(E)	Time	11.0 kHz	11.5 kHz	12.0 kHz	12.5 kHz	10.0 kHz
78,31.058	08,11.865	15:08:58	2.5721	3.9335	3.6789	2.3929	2.7788
78,31.084	08,11.802	15:10:53	2.5883	3.9782	3.7392	2.4317	2.8238
78,31.110	08,11.737	15:12:44	2.6082	4.0269	3.8002	2.4722	2.8705
Site 2							
78,31.099	08,15.783	15:32:34	1.3856	2.6260	3.3385	2.2612	2.3338
78,31.119	08,15.759	15:34:15	1.4626	2.6580	3.3818	2.9397	2.3614
78,31.153	08,15.726	15:36:30	1.9192	2.7074	5.0147	2.9752	2.4070
78,31.187	08,15.680	15:38:43	1.9198	2.7624	5.0567	3.0050	2.4512
Site 3							
78,30.487	08,18.640	16:04:27	3.0643	1.9634	2.8691	3.7086	2.7059
78,30.528	08,18.584	16:07:00	2.9943	1.9481	2.8672	2.8198	2.6747
78,30.561	08,18.526	16:09:11	2.9862	1.9396	2.9098	3.6512	2.6470
Site 4							

78,30.006	08,15.529	16:38:07	3.4704	2.8137	2.0722	1.0472	2.5573
78,30.088	08,15.452	16:43:49	3.2959	2.7266	2.0628	2.8229	2.4283
78,30.115	08,15.431	16:45:37	3.2405	2.7008	2.0645	1.1805	2.3895
78,30.189	08,15.320	16:50:40	3.0894	2.6492	2.0816	2.6826	2.2865
Site 5							
78,30.598	08,12.706	17:13:22	2.6874	1.0166	2.7844	1.4138	2.3189
78,30.631	08,12.605	17:17:01	2.6661	3.4409	2.8475	2.0521	2.3412
78,30.656	08,12.528	17:19:25	2.6557	3.4758	2.8993	2.0532	2.3624
78,30.690	08,12.436	17:22:29	2.6432	3.5218	2.9693	2.0628	2.3920
Site 6							
78,30.666	08,15.078	17:39:03	2.2609	2.5114	2.5547	2.4189	1.9805
78,30.702	08,15.020	17:41:30	2.2144	2.5347	2.6115	2.4148	1.9864
78,30.731	08,14.969	17:43:23	2.1785	2.5609	2.6599	2.4112	1.9950

Table 1.b Interrogation of transponders at the source location from KV Svalbard collected in September 2008.

Position (N)	(E)	Time	11.0 kHz	11.5 kHz	12.0 kHz	12.5 kHz
Site KS 1						
78,31.36229	08,18.50837	12:41:40	2.6187	1.0941	4.2654	4.1965
78,31.35268	08,18.37352	12:43:11	1.5311	2.7585	1.3468	1.0738
78,31.34942	08,18.24620	12:45:11	2.5372	1.4659	1.9721	4.0946
78,31.34955	08,18.18774	12:46:14	2.5174	2.7443	2.9074	4.0696
78,31.35167	08,18.13184	12:47:21	2.4971	2.7429	1.9296	4.0480
78,31.35257	08,18.06432	12:48:30	2.4770	2.7430	4.1536	4.0255
Site KS 2						
78,29.96959	08,18.66935	13:09:02	3.8722	1.2617	2.6517	3.9681
78,29.59910	08,18.72303	13:10:35	3.9101	1.8223	2.6639	3.9950
78,29.95557	08,18.76032	13:11:36	3.9278	1.2381	2.6747	4.0133
78,29.95347	08,18.82367	13:13:17	2.9186	2.5219	2.6939	4.0401
78,29.95401	08,18.86603	13:14:30	3.9610	2.5265	2.7073	4.0564
78,29.95512	08,18.89666	13:15:35	1.5619	2.5273	1.7718	4.0696
Site KS 3						
78,30.02700	08,11.17997	13:35:30	1.4844	4.3047	2.9056	2.6121
78,30.03926	08,11.13934	13:36:24	4.0047	4.3150	2.9210	2.6019
78,30.05413	08,11.09501	13:37:28	3.9944	4.3243	2.9400	2.5903

Deployment of receiver mooring.

August 16 2008 at 3:50 (Z) Håkon Mosby reached the ice edge and we realized that sea ice was covering our pre-selected position at 78 30 N 2:24 E. New drop position 78 26.490 N 2 30.1 E was selected, at where the water depth is 2271 m. The new location is 129.856 km from the source anchor position. Captain selected a deployment track from south starting 9 miles away from the selected drop position. First a south – north bathy track is obtained. This track has very small variability in bathymetry. A W-E bathy 1 nm on each side of the drop point was carried out and the variability was found less than 30 meters. At the selected site the depth is 2270 m. This is roughly 200 m less than the water depth assumed when the mooring was designed, see Figure 9. We therefore, decide to remove a section of 200 m kevlar under the two STARs.

Acoustic releases

We now prepare for testing the releases. The on deck tests for both releases were OK. Started lowering at 04:47 (Z), down at 1000 m at 05:05(Z). Both replies and are confirmed released when they back on deck 06:12(Z). This “exercise” took 1 hour and 25 minutes; meanwhile we started to test the pressure in the STAR tubes (5:00 Z), which was fine. Clock checks were carried out on both SN10 and SN11.

STAR SN11- deepest

At 06:43 (Z) (16 August 2008 - day 229) we start spinning up SN11. This included (1) use PPP to check the clock, (2) Partial disk initialization and (3) disk verification these points was performed and completed. Thereafter, the chirp files was checked and found OK. Experiment Spin-up for SN 11: Mooring 01, Experiment ID: 2008, Bottle 1 (deepest) of 2, “Realtime output” enabled. During the spin-up we got “Garbage” in the console window. We did the spin-up again and the experiment successfully started at **229 07:20:11 (Z)**. Consol window did not open automatically. When we opened the console window no output as expected, then we closed the console and turn off external power. In this case we had to check the console later to be sure that SN 11 was functioning correctly. At 09:00:25 (Z) the SN11 pings and the console window show correct output. Next schedule change for SN 11 is 229 19:20:11. At this point we turned off external power, and instrument was ready for deployment.

STAR SN10 - shallowest

At 9:28(Z) we start to spin up SN10 by commencing the PPP, checking clocks, partial initializing disk, load parameter file into flash memory, checked chirp file. All was reported OK. Spin up SN 10 with mooring ID 1 (western mooring), Exp ID 2008, Bottle ID 0 of 2 and “Realtime output” enabled. Experiment start time is **229 08:07:51 (Z)**. First schedule change is 229 20:07:51. Turned off external power, and SN 10 was ready for deployment.

Mooring deployment

. Hydrophone cable was spooled off and will be fed by hand, and attached to the wire cable, which goes over the block. See figure 10. At 10:34 (Z) the first STAR instrument was deployed The hydrophone cable for each STAR is 300 m was attached to the wire by rubber clamps every one meter kept together by tightened strips. Last hydrophone was 3.2 m from the end of the wire. It was a bit difficult to mate the hydrophone connectors to the STAR, gently heating the outside of connectors helped a lot. At 13:18(Z) the SN11 was deployed.

The attachment of the hydrophone cable went much faster than expected, and we were 1.5 nm away from the planned drop position when we were ready to deploy the anchor. This was too far to tow the mooring so we decided to go 0.5 nm to get into shallower water. Receiver mooring was dropped at 78 25.744 N 2 26.829 E at 15:15:09 at 2292 meter water depth. By pinging the releases the **anchor position was determined to be 78 25.5513 N 2 26.4726 E**, See Figure 11.

After positioning the anchor point, we started to deploy the transponders 1nm from the drop position, see Figure 11. At this point the ice started to come into the area, and we realized that it will not be possible to survey the transponders. Furthermore, the last transponder 1 nm to the east of the deployment site was not deployed as the ice now was almost closing up the deployment area and RV Håkon Mosby had to leave the area. Details of the transponder deployments are found in Table 2.

Positioning of the transponders were postponed to the KV Svalbard cruise in September 2008.

Figure 9. The receiver mooring design. Steel sphere at the top of the mooring and 16 Benthos glass balls provide the required floatation. Mooring is designed so that STAR - SN10 will be at 300 m and STAR – SN 11 will be 989 m under the sea surface given that the depth is 2475 m.

Modems to be used at this mooring is

- 1) SN11 has 852-008
- 2) SN10 has 852-006

AROGOS beacon: SM500 74603

Acoustic Releases are Benthos 850:

41820: Release code A/Enable code C/Interrogation frequency 13 kHz/Reply frequency is 12.5 kHz/48 hours timeout

41093: Release code A/Enable code H/Interrogation frequency 9 kHz/Reply frequency is 10 kHz/48 hours timeout

Hydrophone cables spooled of array-1

Preparing SN10 for deployment. Deployed 10:34 (Z)

Preparing the hydrophone cable to be attached to the wire.

Attaching cable to wire.

Preparing SN 11 for deployment.

Deploying SN 11 at 13:18 (Z).

Launching last cluster of glass balls 14:38 (Z)

...and the dual acoustic releases at 14:44 (Z).

Finally goes the anchor at 15:15(Z)

and finally peace have come to the area.

Figure 10. Deployment of the Receiver mooring 16 August 2008.

Enter initial position of the target

Latitude: 78 deg 25.744 minutes N S
Longitude: 2 deg 26.829 minutes W E
Depth (m): 2280

Number of Surveys: 12

Push EDIT and enter your survey positions with this format:
Lat(deg) Lat(min) lon(deg) lon(min) travel_time (secs)
 1-way 2-way

Ave. Soundspeed (m/s): 1460 Transponder depth (m): 5

Calculated lat,lon position is:

lat N: 78 deg 25.5513 min
lon E: 2 deg 26.4726 min

Figure 11. After the deployment of the Anchor at 78 25.744 N 2 26.829 E. A survey with the ship was carried to ping the acoustic releases using the Benthos deck unit to estimate the anchor position. This positioning has to be done during the deployment cruise as the releases have a 48 hours time out.

New anchor position was calculated (by Matlab program obtained from Arthur Newhall) to be 78 25.5513 N 2 26.4726 E corresponding depth was estimated to 2280+5 m

However, the water depth is 2296 +/-1 m from the ship data logg. Ship echo sounder use a sound speed of 1475 m/s, however the mean sound speed is closer to 1460 m/s. This introduce an error, which has to be corrected for.

Table 2.a Transponders deployed roughly 1 nm from the drop position. All transponders was deployed right aft.

Transponder-ID	Release code	X-mit freq	RCV freq	Deploy	GMT time	Drop Position-GPS (From ship log, based on GPS time)	Depth (Echo sounder)
TR6001/41928	F	12.5 kHz	9.0 KHz	North	17:07:33	78 25.655 N 2 21.514 E	2349.5
TR6001/41922	C	11.0 kHz	9.0 KHz	East	17:28:45	78 26.62272 N, 02 27.87668 E	2270
TR6001/41920	E	12.0 kHz	9.0 KHz	South	18:13:40	78 24.724673 N, 02 24.366027 E	2458
TR6001/41914	D	11.5 kHz	9.0 KHz	West	Not deployed		

The McLane Profiler

The McLane Profiler was deployed 17 August 2008. This was an anchor first deployment, while the tomography moorings were anchor last deployments. The profiler mooring design is shown in Figure 12. The 1500 m long jacketed wire rope on which the McLane profiler will slide up and down on once a day made the deployment quite time demanding. The wire had to be spooled in and out several times before the profiler could be added on and deployed. Anchor/releases were hung over the ship side at 11:48 (Z). At 20:20 (Z) it was confirmed that the Benthos transponder and the ORE offshore 8242x5 release responded to deck units.

The McLane profiler.

Figure 12. Mooring design for the McLane Profiler.

Acoustic release: ORE offshore 8242x5. Release number 32656. Enable A 666433, Interrogate 11kHz, Reply frequency 12 kHz (pulse 10 msec).

Benthos transponder: Serial number 44387/Receiver frequency 10 kHz, Transmit 12.0 kHz/Enable code A.

Acoustic modem.

The acoustic modems on the source mooring and on the receiver moorings were all interrogated by the deck unit. All replied, but no successful data download.

Figure 13. The deck modem was hung over the side of the ship roughly 15 m below the sea surface.

Figure 14. Map of the transmitting ARGOS buoys 15-16 August 2008. (From IMR, Østensen)

Summary

Except for the tests of the modems, which did not give satisfactory results, all the objectives of the experiment were carried out successfully.

All instruments were carefully tested; except for a unstable logging of the acoustic receptions in SN 11 the instruments were fine. Worst case noticed for SN 11 was a 50 % failure in logging the receptions, best case was failure in 1 out of 6 receptions. There was no obvious solution to this problem, which is most likely due to an “instability” interplay between the software and hardware. Despite the instability in the SN11, we decided to deploy all the instruments.

Another detail to notice and remember till next time, is the ARGOS beacons, which did not transmit before they were in sea. However, positions of transmissions from ARGOS 15-16, see Figure 14, are fine.

In Figure 15a,b the positions of the tomography moorings are shown in two SAR images. They clearly show how close the receiver mooring was deployed the ice edge, and how a vortex pair was developing the next 48 hours. This indicates clearly the dynamics in the area and how interesting the acoustic data will be to analyze. The CTD section in Figure 16 is obtained from west to east during the 17-18 August along the acoustic track. Positions of the CTD stations are indicated in Figure 15 by yellow squares.

Figure 15 a. Source mooring in red, receiver mooring in blue, and CTD stations in yellow are overlaid the ASAR image from 16 August 2008.

Figure 15 b. Source mooring in red, receiver mooring in blue, and CTD stations in yellow are overlaid the ASAR image from 18 August 2008.

Figure 16. Oceanographic section obtained 17-18 August along the acoustic track.

Cruise report

Acoustic tomography experiment in the Fram Strait

KV Svalbard 19-26 September 2008

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Introduction.

During 19-26 September 2008 the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) and collaborators conducted a 7 days long scientific field experiment in the Fram Strait between Greenland and Svalbard.

Most of the allocated ship time onboard the KV Svalbard was used to follow up the tomography experiment by listening to the source at different locations, attempt to download acoustic data using acoustic modems and to complete the deployment and positioning of transponders around the receiver mooring. In connection with an acoustic ice stations within the ice edge it was decided to add on sea ice measurements. This latter activity is part of the PRODEX project.

Furthermore, time was spent to recover two DAMOCLES moorings and to pick up the DAMOCLES sea glider. Figure 1 show the positions of the tomography moorings and the McLane profiler relative to the ice edge two days after the deployment. It also shows the position of the AWI winch mooring and the UMPC MOPS mooring.

The experiment objectives.

The primary objectives of the cruise was:

- 1) **Acoustic propagation study.** Carry out an acoustic propagation study using a short hydrophone array launched from KV Svalbard at different locations along the acoustic track, inside and outside the ice edge. Oceanographic measurements along the acoustic track using XBTs and a mini CTD.
- 2) **Acoustic modem testing.** Download of processed acoustic data and navigation data from the source and receiver moorings using acoustic modem.
- 3) **Deployment and positioning of transponders.** Deploy one remaining transponder at the receiver location. Use the Benthos transponder to position the four transponders surrounding the receiver mooring.
- 4) **Recovery of AWI mooring and glider.** Recover the winch mooring at Mooring position 78°49'N and 06°00'E and recover the glider close to this position.
- 5) **Recovery of MOPS mooring.** Position and recover the MOPS mooring at 80° 36.1N 07° 15.7E

To plan the field activities we used ASAR data covering our area in combination with the weather forecasts. Some changes in the planned time schedule was made, but all tasks were carried out with minor deviations from plan. In this report we describe how the cruise was carried out task by task, and finally a small summary of results obtained is provided.

Figure 1. SAR image from 18 August 2008 overlaid the position of the source mooring (red), the Receiver mooring (blue), the IOPAN MMP (green), the AWI winch mooring (black) and the UPMC MOPS mooring (yellow).

Cruise Diary.

Date DD/MM	Time	Day	Main task.	Specific Tasks
19/9	9:00	Friday	Loading	Enter and load ship in Longyearbyen NERSC, AWI and UMPC were responsible for bringing their own equipment onboard. Help was provided from KV Svalbard crew to load the ship..

19/9	15:00		Departure	
	22:10 -1:10		Source mooring	<p>Source Station 78 30.6333 N 8 15.0943 E.</p> <p>Listening to source using the hydrophone from the side of the ship 02:10. No obvious sign of the source. Most likely to noisy to “see” the source without any signal processing.</p> <p>No response from the Aquatec modem. It was concluded that communication most likely was not established due to noisy ship.</p> <p>Sea was to “rough” (mainly due to swell) to use the small boat to get away from the ship. Therefore, based on weather forecast, we dropped further listening at source position and the positions between the source, and ship headed directly to the receiver position. The receiver position was closer to the ice edge and we therefore expected less fetch for wind-generated waves.</p>
20/09	11:00	Saturday		receiver position.
			Hydrophone Modem Positioning of the transponders	<p>Receiver station 78 25.513 N 2 26.4726 E: 130 km from the source.</p> <p>11:58. Deployed the last transponder using crane over the rear.</p> <p>12:00-14:00. Positioning of the four transponders. Accurate GPS time/position was obtained from the ship, travel times was obtained from the deck unit and written by hand. Positioning was completed at 14:00.</p> <p>13:30 At receiver position we listen to source signal using the hydrophone cable from the small boat.</p> <p>15:00-18:00 Prepared the modem to download the data using the small boat “Sjøbjørn”. Obtained some NAV data and hopefully some acoustic data from each modem.</p> <p>12:00-15:30 Preparation of the CTD winch. CTD software works on Agnieszkas PC and we are ready to do CTD.</p> <p>19:30 First CTD attempt. At 19:50 the CTD is stuck in the propeller. Crew in motor boats and divers tries to get the CTD back. Rescue operation terminated at 22:30.</p> <p>Meeting on the bridge at 23:00. Sea state is not optimal for listening and using the modem from the small boat. Stronger winds are expected. Cannot go westward to reach the ice edge as we then enter the Danish zone, and we decide to go Northwards along 0-1 E latitude. Given the location of the ice edge we will go into the ice pack tomorrow morning and look for the first ice station. Keep within Norwegian water and check the bathymetry to avoid being in a “shadow” zone for source listening</p>
21/09	8:00	Sunday		8:00 Penetrated the ice edge at 79 08.6 N 001 07.1 E.

	15:08		Hydrophone Ice station	<p>Ice station 79 27.204 N 00 24.83 E.</p> <p>Main purpose listening to the source, secondary purpose ice measurements.</p> <p>Floe size 60m x120 m.</p> <p>17:10. Acoustic listening 79 26.312 N 0 20.704 E (NB! People on the ice tried to start drilling at 17:10 they was stopped just after)</p> <p>17:20. Start drilling holes in ice for ice thickness measurements. However, the freshwater ice on top of the floe was very hard to get through with the tools we had available from UNIS. Just three holes were drilled and the EM was used for three sections.</p> <p>18:00 Meeting at the bridge. Weather forecast shows wind from North the next days and this is favorable for picking up UPMC mooring, which is close to the ice edge (in the North). Furthermore, the ship noise in acoustic data is dominating the recordings. This cannot be reduced because we cannot get a totally silent ship or move away from the ship using small boat in the ice.</p> <p>Based on this we decide to move to the UPMC position to do mooring recovery Monday noon. Can be there at 12:00 Monday. Furthermore, weather forecast indicates favorable wind conditions on Wednesday for glider recovery. Acoustic recordings and ice work on Tuesday. According to this, the glider is now programmed to be in recovery modus and close to AWI mooring on morning 24 September (Wednesday).</p> <p>20:00. Swell starts to be visually from the bridge (compression and decompression of the ice field). Estimated period is 23 s.</p> <p>20:10 Acoustic listening at 79 25.439 N 00 13.826 E. Wind is blowing from north at 24.7 knot. Effective temperature is -18 C.</p> <p>23:10 Acoustic listening 79 24.47 N 00 08.084 N</p> <p>23:30 Ice people and acousticians onboard the ship.</p> <p>Depth at the ice station at 23:30 2745 m. Please note that the sonar cannot be used during transit in ice or during acoustic work.</p>
22/09		Monday		UPMC mooring recovery
22/09	24:00- 11:30		Transit Mooring recovery	<p>UPMC site 80 30 N 7 E.</p> <p>MOPS Mooring recovery.</p> <p>11:28: 80 31.66 N 07 07.898 E close to mooring. Sea-state: a few white caps and some scattered ice.</p> <p>12:15 Mooring located by the ship sonar. Calm wind but significant swell.</p>

			<p>12:20 Sonar stopped, to not disturb with the release signal</p> <p>12:40 Prepare and send release signal.</p> <p>12:50 Release successful, and buoy observed short after.</p> <p>13:10 Crane is lowered, propellers stopped. Try to hook on the crane from Sjøbjørn. Strong tension on the wire makes it difficult to get the hook on. Move the ship to get to a better position.</p> <p>15:00 Mission completed.</p> <p>15:45 Moves North-westward to do more acoustic recordings inside ice edge and to do ice thickness measurements on selected ice floes.</p>
			<p>Ice station 2: Acoustic recordings and ice measurements</p> <p>15:48 Move into the diffuse ice edge (30 % ice) 80 41.942 N 6 11.36 E</p> <p>17:05 Relaxed ice conditions and relatively low ice concentration. Ice floes too small for ice stations. 80 42.327 N 04 45.10 E</p> <p>18:15 Found a large enough ice floe. Five people prepare to work on the ice. 80 42.58 N 04 33.407 E. Small wind generated waves. Floe is thicker than 2 m.</p> <p>19:25 Acousticicians go to a location close to a relatively compact ice edge.</p> <p>20:10 Acoustic listening. Position 80 42.631N 4 32.046 E.</p> <p>20:50 All People on the ship. Very cold conditions -4.8 C and strong wind from North.</p>
23/9			<p>More acoustic listening and ice measurements</p> <p>08:10 Small boat at the first listening position 80 32.443 N 05 00.780 E. Acoustic listening a bit problematic as the boat was drifting and the hydrophone array was tilting with up to 45 degrees. Strong wind, but small waves.</p> <p>8:30-9:00 Ice characterized with scattered ice floes large bands of film of grease ice ≈30 %.. 9:30</p> <p>9:50 At 80 34.422 N 4 18.59 E. Areas with dense ice. Floes are 5-10 m in diameter with partly frozen slush in between. Ship moves westward and open areas can be observed 300 m away in northward direction.</p> <p>11:10 Ship heading 280 degrees. Position 80 35.949N 4 10.69 E. Ice condition: 80 % starboard and open lead on port side. Acoustic measurement in small boat 1nm away from KV Svalbard.</p> <p>11:25 Move into compact ice. 80-90% concentration and floe size -2-5 m. No visual swell.</p> <p>12:40 Position 80 34.930 N 3 55.08 E. Ice floes are between 5-50 m.</p>

				<p>12:55 Floe located and ready to go out on the ice to do ice measurements. MY Floe is surrounded by compact refrozen broken ice floes. No acoustic measurement at this location because of no possibility to reduce the impact of ship noise.</p> <p>13:15 Ice station launched.</p> <p>13:55 Position 80 34.350 N 3 54.568 E. Heading 256 degrees. T=-5.7 C and W= 23.9 knop. Very cold.</p> <p>14:30 People onboard the ship again. Decided to work on floe close to KV Svalbard since walking over the cracks seemed hazardous. Started ice drilling but lost the tip of the drill, and decided to measure ice thickness in cracks. Did 3 thickness measurements on cracks with corresponding EM measurements.</p> <p>16:25 Acoustic measurement. Position Sjøbjørn 80 29.795 N 04 18.090 E. Position KV Svalbard (16:05) 80 30.850 N 004 08.618 E. Wind 25 knot.</p> <p>Heading towards the position of the AWI mooring/glider in order to be at location tomorrow morning. Calm wind and wave conditions as expected from weather forecast.</p>
24/9				Glider and mooring recovery at the AWI site
24/09	09:40		Glider & mooring	<p>09:40 Waiting for Glider recovery 78:43.571 N 06:31.97E</p> <p>10:00 Glider position from Optimare 78:44.015N 006:25.13E</p> <p>10:10 Glider visually observed from KV Svalbard. Small boat launched.</p> <p>10:33 Glider in small boat.</p> <p>10 :25 Glider successfully onboard KV Svalbard.</p> <p>11:00 Start the mooring recovery. Problems in sending the release code from KV Svalbard due to ship noise.</p> <p>13:02 Successful release from small boat.</p> <p>13:04 Floatation observed.</p> <p>13:07 Two small boats on the location .</p> <p>13:23 Lower and upper part of the mooring under control of the two small boats.</p> <p>13:43 Winch and floatation on deck. Profiler+microcats lost.</p> <p>15:13 Releases and floatation on deck.</p>
24/9				Listening to the source at different locations every 3 hour. Start 17:10. See table for positions
25/9	19:00		Acoustics Transit to	<p>12:15-13:45 Acoustic modem test at the source location</p> <p>14:00-16:00: Transponder positioning at the source location</p>

			LYR	Summary meeting on the bridge at 19:00. 20:10 Last acoustic listening. The acoustic listening at 17:10 failed do to a bad electric connection. Start transit to Longyearbyen.
26/9	09:00		LYR offload	Back in Longyearbyen. Offload the ship. All participants took part in the off load. Each partner organized their need for transport and logistics in Longyearbyen. Flight at 14:45.

Fig 2. Ship track during the cruise plotted with white dots every four-hour with a line between plotted on the ASAR image from 20 September 2008. Source position is marked by red, blue is the receiver location, yellow is the acoustic listening positions, green is the UPMC-MOPS mooring position, turquoise is the ice station positions, orange is the AWI mooring position, and lilac is the glider retrieval position.

Task 1. Sound propagation study.

The aim of this Task was to

- Carry out an acoustic propagation study using a short hydrophone array launched from KV Svalbard at different locations along the acoustic track, inside and outside the ice edge.
- Oceanographic measurements along the acoustic track using XBTs and mini CTD.
- Carry out ice stations at acoustic measurement sites inside the ice edge.

This part of the experiment was carried out according to the revised work plan for NERSC in DAMOCLES WP3&WP8 (February 2008).

The tomographic system consists of a tomographic source position at 78 30.6333 N 8 15.0943 E and the receiver anchor position at 78 25.513 N 2 26.4726 E. This system was deployed by RV Håkon Mosby 15-16 August. Distance between moorings is calculated (using WGS 84 ellipsoid) to be 130 010 m. The source transmit 60 s long sweeps from 190 to 290 Hz every third hour (00:10, 3:10, 6:10, 9:10, 12:10, 15:10, 18:10, 21:1 all times given in GMT). The hydrophone array was used at 20 measurement sites during the KV Svalbard cruise out of which 11 measurements were made along the acoustic track between source and receiver.

Below we provide a summary acoustic experiment, the collection of oceanographic data and sea ice data.

Acoustic experiment

The experiment is designed to provide data to be able to compare acoustic measurements with modelled acoustic arrival structure, travel times and amplitudes. Acoustic measurements were planned to be made at different distances from the source, within and outside the ice edge. These measurements are then processed to detect observed arrival time structure. These observations are planned to be compared to model predicted arrival times.

An oceanographic section between the source and receiver was obtained by use of XBTs from KV Svalbard. Modeled acoustic arrival times will be generated by using oceanographic fields, obtained by combining XT data collected during this cruise and CTD section obtained during RV Håkon Mosby cruise earlier, as input to appropriate propagation models.

Acoustic Measurements

The acoustic recordings were made by lowering a hydrophone array consisting of 4 individual acoustic sensors to ca 100 meters depth. The hydrophone array was attached to a cable that was connected to a surface logging unit. The recordings were initially carried out using the coast guard vessel as platform. It turned out that the vessel was acoustically too noisy to carry out measurements. Thus, in open seas the measurements were carried out by deploying the hydrophone array from the small boat "Sjøbjørn" at ca 1 nm distance from the coast guard vessel, leaving the small boat drifting. While significantly reducing the impact of vessel noise in the recordings, noise due to vibrations induced in the hydrophone cable could still be observed, especially for measurements carried out at high wind speeds, with large drift speed. In areas of diffuse ice, measurements were also carried out using ice floats as platform. However, with the vessel in close range to the float, thus still contributing to measurement noise. In diffuse ice areas with low enough ice concentration to allow the small boat to be used, the small boat towed to ice flows was used as platform in an attempt to reduce cable drift

induced vibrations. The ice flows were more scattered having some drift under these conditions, such that some cable vibrations remained.

A total of 20 acoustical recordings were carried out. Reference is made to table 1 for an overview of the recordings. The positions of the acoustic recordings are plotted onto a ASAR image in Figure 3.

A first glance at the data.

The most important aim of the acoustic measurements was to confirm that the source is transmitting according to the pre-programmed schedule. This has been achieved see Figure 4. By analyzing the recorded data using time-frequency analysis, the signature of the source can be easily identified in the spectrogram as shown in figure 4. The straight line clearly visible in the figure represents the frequency modulated sweep from 190 Hz to 290 Hz emitted by the source over duration of one minute.

It is clearly observed from the data that the attenuation of the signals increases with distance to the source. For instance, as is evident from Figure 4, the source signal is much weaker at 60 km distances from the source, than at close range. At the receiver position and location further away the signal is not easily seen and the data has to go through a more careful analysis. This fully agrees with theory and what we expected. The acoustic measurements will go through signal processing to detect the arrival time structure, using correlation with the known chirp of the source. The collected data set will thereafter compared to modelling results be used to study the ability of the selected models to predict travel times and transmission loss in the Fram Strait Environment.

Recommendation.

For the future, improvements in the hydrodynamic design of the hydrophone cable should be considered to cope with drifting measurement platforms. In addition, to exploit large ice flows and compact ice as a stable and low noise platform, one should consider the use of the vessel's helicopter to quickly depart some nautical miles from the vessel for deployment of the hydrophone from such ice flows. Another option would be to deploy sonobuoys from the ship, and then leave the area for listening. However, both options would require additional funding.

Figure 3a. Acoustic listening at the first ice station.

Test no	Filename (Date_time)	Conditions	Platform	Measurement Position
1	1_2008-9-20_0-8-5.wav	Water	Vessel "Svalbard"	"Source"
2	1_2008-9-20_12-8-8.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	"Receiver"
3	1_2008-9-21_9-8-5.wav	Ice (diffuse)	Vessel "Svalbard"	79:18N 0:45,41E
4	1_2008-9-21_12-8-39.wav	Ice (diffuse)	Vessel "Svalbard"	79:27,351N 0:03,586E
5	1_2008-9-21_15-9-12.wav	Ice (diffuse)	Icefloat, vessel 100m away	79:25,860N 0:17,781E
6	1_2008-9-21_18-8-20.wav	Ice (diffuse)	Icefloat, vessel 100m away	79:25,860N 0:17,781E
7	1_2008-9-21_21-8-17.wav	Ice (diffuse)	Icefloat, vessel 100m away	79:25,860N 0:17,781E
8	1_2008-9-22_18-8-13.wav	Ice (diffuse)	Small Boat towed to icefloat	80:42,631N 4:32,056E
9	1_2008-9-23_6-8-5.wav	Ice (diffuse)	Small boat drifting	80:32,423N 5:00,780E
10	1_2008-9-23_9-8-18.wav	Ice (diffuse)	Small Boat towed to icefloat	80:34,711N 4:09,213E
11	1_2008-9-23_14-13-2.wav	Ice (diffuse)	Small Boat towed to icefloat	80:22,920N 5:09,309E
12	1_2008-9-24_15-7-28.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	78:32,141N 5:38,858E
13	1_2008-9-24_18-8-13.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	78:27,969N 5:32,060E
14	1_2008-9-24_21-8-22.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	78:29,038N 6:00,622E
15	1_2008-9-25_0-8-27.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	78:28,143N 6:28,139E
16	1_2008-9-25_3-8-9.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	78:28,437N 6:54,143E
17	1_2008-9-25_6-8-12.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	78:29,329N 7:19,636E
18	1_2008-9-25_9-8-1.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	78:30,532N 7:46,939E
19	1_2008-9-25_12-8-58.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	78:30,740N 8:14,966E
20	1_2008-9-25_18-8-10.wav	Water	Small boat drifting	78:32,483N 9:17,535E

Table 1: Overview of acoustical recordings

Figure 4. Upper spectrogram shows recordings at close range (< 1 km) to the source position. The straight line represents a frequency modulated sweep from 190 to 290 Hz over duration of 60 sec (from 62 ses to 122 sec along time axis). The acoustic intensity is represented in colours. The red colour of the signal represents more energy than the green/blue caused by ambient noise. (Test no 19). Similarly, the lower spectrogram shows acoustic recordings at 60 km distance from the source (test no 12). Signal is obviously weaker than at close range to the source.

Oceanographic data

During the KV Svalbard cruise 16 XBTs were deployed in the eastern and central Fram Strait along the latitude 78°30' N. Over the shelf slope XBTs were launched with the 3 Nm step, in the deep part with the 6 Nm step. Each instrument measured pressure and temperature profile down to ca. 460m, except of last two devices, which were torn off at 256m and 225m, respectively. Raw data files included also a position of the ship when XBT were launched and a total depth measured by the ship's sonar.

To obtain the full depth temperature profiles and estimates of the sound velocity, XBT data were combined with CTD data measured in July 2008 during the ARKXXIII/2 cruise of RV Polarstern in Fram Strait. The summer section was measured along 78°50'N (20 Nm northward of the XBT section done by KV Svalbard), thus the bottom bathymetry varied to some extent between two sections.

For each XBT temperature profile the complementary CTD station at 78°50'N was found, based on the bottom contour rather than longitude (using 'stream coordinates'). Next, XBT temperature profile in the upper layer was combined with temperature profile in deep water from a CTD station (below the Atlantic water layer) and the gap between, if existed, was filled by cubic interpolation. This should introduce relatively small error while temperature in deep layers in the northern Fram Strait reveals no significant seasonal variations. Finally, all reconstructed profiles were cut according to a depth measured by the ship's sonar at 78°30'N. To obtain sound velocity profiles, the reconstructed temperature profiles were used together with respective salinity profiles, measured at 78°50'N. While in the studied region a sound velocity is mostly dependent on a temperature and changes of salinity along the stream coordinates are small, error in sound velocity due to using of salinity profiles from the northern section should be negligible.

Cross section and profiles of temperature from raw XBT data and cross section and profiles of temperature and sound velocity from combined data are shown in Figure 5-9.

Figure 5. Positions of XBTs launched from KV Svalbard in September 2008

Table 2. List of XBT casts

Cruise	Station	Type	mon/day/yr	hh:mm	Lon (°E)	Lat (°N)	Depth (m)
KV Svalbard	FS01	XBT	09/19/2008	22:45	9.3658	78.5208	502
KV Svalbard	FS02	XBT	09/19/2008	23:03	9.1283	78.5182	704
KV Svalbard	FS03	XBT	09/19/2008	23:22	8.8762	78.5175	880
KV Svalbard	FS04	XBT	09/19/2008	23:41	8.6283	78.5133	1118
KV Svalbard	FS05	XBT	09/20/2008	00:00	8.3650	78.5100	1259
KV Svalbard	FS06	XBT	09/20/2008	03:33	8.1150	78.5067	1506
KV Svalbard	FS07	XBT	09/20/2008	04:07	7.6133	78.5000	1976
KV Svalbard	FS08	XBT	09/20/2008	04:42	7.1067	78.4917	2896
KV Svalbard	FS09	XBT	09/20/2008	05:18	6.6417	78.4850	2457
KV Svalbard	FS10	XBT	09/20/2008	05:55	6.0917	78.4800	1867
KV Svalbard	FS11	XBT	09/20/2008	06:31	5.6617	78.4717	1578
KV Svalbard	FS12	XBT	09/20/2008	07:06	5.1500	78.4800	1853
KV Svalbard	FS13	XBT	09/20/2008	07:41	4.6700	78.4550	2108
KV Svalbard	FS14	XBT	09/20/2008	08:18	4.1583	78.4450	2147
KV Svalbard	FS15	XBT	09/20/2008	08:54	3.6517	78.4417	2187
KV Svalbard	FS16	XBT	09/20/2008	09:30	3.1750	78.4417	2178

Figure 5. Temperature cross section along 78°30'N from XBT data(white lines indicate a position and depth of measurement)

Figure 6. Collection of individual temperature profiles measured by XBT dropped from KV Svalbard along 78°30'N in September 2008

Figure 7. Cross section of temperature based on combined data from XBT in the upper layer of 460m (September 2008) and CTD data in deep waters below 700m (July 2008)

Figure 8. Cross section of sound velocity based on combined data from XBT in the upper layer of 460m (September 2008) and CTD data in deep waters below 700m (July 2008)

Figure 9. Collection of individual sound velocity profiles based on combined data from XBT in the upper layer of 460m (September 2008) and CTD data in deep waters below 700m (July 2008)

Sea ice work at Ice stations.

Introduction

During the Acoustic tomography experiment in the Fram Strait two opportunities for ice stations were given. One was 9 hours long, and the other 24 hours. The ice stations were planned for the project Prodex with the objective to

- See how freeboard correlates to ice thickness and how that is affected by a snow cover and melt water ponds. A denser drilling near ridges would also give a picture on how ridges affects the freeboard of the surrounding thinner ice, and the spatial scale of this.

Experiment setup

The aim was to find an ice floe with varying topography and measure the ice thickness, ice freeboard, snow thickness along several transects on the ice floe. In addition ice cores and snow samples should be taken to measure the densities of both snow and ice.

The equipment available for the ice stations was:

2m of 2" drill, with a manual crank.
Ice core drill
EM-31 em induction instrument on a sledge
Snow density kit
Iron rod with a hook in the end to measure ice thickness
A folding rule

Measurements

The ice measurements were made on three different ice floes. The first ice floe was located in the area 79.5 deg N 0.5 deg E. It was a thick multi year ice with a ridge on one side and thinner ice on two sides near the edge. The bottom side was flooded with sea water and there were two melt pools next to the large ridge. There was no snow on top of the ice. A sketch of the floe can be seen in figure 10.

The drilling equipment was not sufficient for the thick ice, so the plan of drilling transects had to be abandoned. Instead, measurements of freeboard and thickness along the edge of the ice were made by using a long rod with a hook in the end, to find the bottom of the ice floe. The edge needed to be very sharp for this to be possible however, and no more than five measurements, M01-M05, could be made.

Sections could still be made with the EM-31, but since it needs to be calibrated to ice thickness by drilling holes, they could only be made on the thinner parts of the ice floe. Section 1 was made from the ship diagonally across the floe along the ridge, see figure 10. Section 2 was made from the ridge to the other corner of the ice floe. Finally, section 3 was made along the thinner ice close to the upper edge of the ice floe. In vicinity to the sections, four holes were drilled, marked H1-H4. Of these, only hole H2 and H3 got through the ice, and they were together with edge measurement M04 used for calibration of the EM-31. Results from the EM-31 are presented in figure 10

The second ice floe was located in the area around 80.5 deg north and 5 deg east, due to the limitations in drilling equipment, a small, about 35 m in diameter, thin ice floe was chosen. A sketch of the floe can be seen in figure 11a, with the measurement points marked. The floe was bare from snow and with a hard layer of ice the upper 0,5 m.

Five holes, H1-H5, were drilled as a cross, where ice thickness and freeboard was measured. In addition, one ice core, C1, was taken close to the middle of the ice floe, and six measurements of ice thickness and freeboard were made from the edge of the floe, M01-M06. Like on the first ice floe, it

was surprisingly difficult to do these measurements, an uneven ice edge made it difficult to find the bottom of the ice and melting of the edge above water made it rounded and difficult to get a correct freeboard. The ice floe was considered too small to use the EM-31, the vicinity to open water would affect the measurements too much.

Ice floe 3 was located in the area of 80.5 deg north and 4.5 deg east, it was a multi year floe about 40x30 meters with one larger ridge, between 0.8 and 1 meter high and three meltponds. The floe was covered in a very hard and slippery upper layer, about 0.5 meters thick.

In the first hole that was drilled, the water flowing into it while drilling froze and the drill got stuck. After some work all but the drill crown was freed, but all further drilling was stopped since it would only lead to loss of more equipment. Thickness measurements were made in the cracks of the ice floe, marked in figure 11b as edge measurements. One section was made with the EM-31, and it was calibrated over the cracks where edge measurements were made. One ice core of the upper meter of the ice was taken near the section.

Figure 10. Ice thickness measurements on ice floe at ice station 1. Blue areas are melt water pools or flooded sea ice, dark areas are ridges and turquoise are areas with thinner bluish ice.

First glance on the data

The original objective, how freeboard varies over an ice floe and how the freeboard-thickness relationship varies in proximity of for example ridges and meltwater pools could not be measured with the equipment we had. Many more drill holes and sections would have been necessary for this. From the measurements that were made however, see fig. 12a and 12b below, something like a linear trend can be seen in between freeboard and ice thickness as expected. When plotting the ratio between freeboard and ice thickness towards ice thickness, it seems they can be related as well. Thicker ice

seems to have a higher ratio of freeboard/thickness. This is consistent with the measurements that thicker ice has a lower density, much due to brine drainage leaving cavities in the ice.

Recommendations for next cruise

A discussion with Kenneth Johansen at Aker Solutions on how to measure freeboard without having to drill holes by using a laser water level lead to a suggestion of a new method for examining freeboard and thickness variations.

By placing a laser water level on a flat area of the ice floe, the water level of the ocean can be measured relative to the laser instrument. By then measuring the ice level, the freeboard can be calculated. Together with an EM-31, thickness and freeboard can be measured in a dense grid, with only a few drilled holes to calibrate the EM-instrument. The time consuming drilling can then be concentrated around ridges where the EM-31 is underestimating ice thickness. The equipment needed for this method is presented in table 3.

Figure 11a. Overview of ice floe 2 with measurement points marked as red dots and ridges with their height as gray areas

Figure 11b. Ice floe of ice station 3. Thinner black lines are cracks in the ice floe. Dimensions of the floe are about 40x30 meters

Figure 12a. Scatter diagram of ice thickness vs. ice freeboard from all ice floes.

Figure 12b. Scatter diagram of ice thickness vs. freeboard/thickness ratio from all ice floes.

Table 3. Recommended equipment for an ice station in the Fram strait during autumn with the objective to examine the relationship between ice thickness and ice freeboard.

<i>Drilling and measuring equipment:</i>
At least 5 m of 2 inch drills
2 x Drill crowns for the 2" drill
Drill engine
Petrol for drill engine
Adapter to fit the 2" drills to the engine
Ice core drill
Adapter for engine to ice core drill
Laser level (up to 300m range) with tripod and a yard stick
EM-31 with sledge
Stick for measuring ice thickness through holes, with 5 cm accuracy
Snow density kit
A scales up to 5kg with 1 gram accuracy
Ruler (foldable)
Thermometer for air and water
<i>For documentation and safety:</i>
Camera
Watch
GPS
Clipboard or a small book (for notes, A4 papers too big)
Crampons
Headlamp
Spikes (to get out of the water with)
Life jackets

Explanation deviation from objective of the Task 1.

- A different distribution of recording points along the acoustic track was obtained than planned. This was mainly due to the weather conditions, and the fact that we had to do recordings from the small boat and not from the KV Svalbard. Due to strong noise from the KV Svalbard disturbing the acoustic measurements, the small boat “Sjøbjørn” was used as platform for the acoustic measurements. This was a very good solution during good environmental conditions. However, the use of the small boat was limited in heavy swell/wave conditions both due to the safety and influence of increased and variable drag in the underwater cable on the acoustic recordings. The use of the small boat in compact sea ice was of course impossible.
- The plan was to use the mini CTD to obtain temperature/salinity data. The Mini CTD was lost on the first cast and therefore no CTD data was obtained.
- The ice work was partly hampered by to minimized amount of drilling equipment.

Task 2. Acoustic modem testing

At the Receiver mooring, communications were established with both modems. The interrogations confirmed that both modems had been recording data from the STAR receivers, and that the amount of stored data on each was consistent with the duration of the deployment up to the time of interrogation (494560 bytes on unit 6 and 473045 bytes on unit 8). Following several periods of interrogation attempts, a small amount of data was retrieved from each modem (240 bytes from unit 6 and 362 bytes from unit 8). When examined, it was clear that the data was potentially valid STAR data, but the data fragments were too small to contain scientifically useful information.

During data transmission, the uncorrected symbol error rate (i.e. the proportion is approximately 7%. Despite this, only 39% of data was successfully transmitted.

There are several reasons for the limited data download as follows:

- The interrogation process dictated by the software can require an unnecessarily high degree of repeated communications, which consumed a lot of time in an environment with high bit error rates before proper data downloads were attempted.
- The modem’s data block reception routines were unnecessarily intolerant of data errors. If a block of 10 data packets contained one packet with 3 or more symbol errors (i.e. unrecoverable errors) then not only was the packet rejected, but also the entire block.
- The high speed data rate that was available for data uploads was never tried due to the somewhat difficult operating conditions.

At the Source mooring, communications with the modem were never established. Acoustic recordings indicate that the modem responded to some interrogations, but that the signals were never fully decoded by the surface unit. There are two possible causes for this communications failure:

- One of the frequencies used in the communications signalling matches the receive frequency of one of the transponding acoustic releases at the Source mooring. The reply frequency of the transponder is also one of the communications frequencies. Some recordings appear to show this device transponding – even though it should now be dormant – and that would interfere with successful communications.

- On the recordings there also appears to be a constant signal mid-way between two of the systems operating frequencies. Although out of band, this could also influence the decoding.

During the cruise, several recordings were made of acoustic communication that can now be further analyzed to assist in improving performance in this environment. Although they will not yield any new data, the mechanisms of symbol and packet failure can now be fully assessed.

Although the amount of data retrieved was disappointing, the interrogations have shown that the STAR receivers appear to be gathering the correct amount of data. A substantial collection of acoustic data means that there is, for the first time in the project, some good deep water communications data to work on to improve algorithms and reliability.

With the receiver moorings, the basic commanding performance of the modems was good. This has important implications for other modems already deployed, since we can be confident that communications can be established with them. With the additional acoustic information available, improvements can be made to the reception and processing of data packets that will remain compatible with those units already deployed. Firmware upgrades can then be made available to other modems such as those in the AITPs (Acoustic Ice tethered Platforms).

Figure 13. Preparing the modem deck unit.

Figure 14 . Contacting the modem at the source mooring through PC connected to the acoustic modem.

Task 3. Deployment and positioning of transponders

Our task was to deploy one remaining transponder at the receiver location, and furthermore to use the Benthos transponder to position the four transponders surrounding the receiver mooring.

On 20th September the fourth transponder at the mooring position was successfully deployed from the rear of KV Svalbard at 78 25.363 N 02 31.343 E. Procedure is shown in the photo sequence in Figure 15. The depth obtained from the ship sonar was 2104 m (± 10 -20m) from the sea surface to sea floor.

Thereafter, a positioning survey as carried out. Seven sites, as shown in map in Figure 16, was visited. At each site five to six interrogations were made with the transducer hanging out from the side of the ship approximately 9 meters under the surface. Each interrogation position is plotted in the figure 16 and show how the ship was “drifting” under each site stop. The GPS time and position was logged during the survey. The accuracy of the ship GPS is 1 m

Additional interrogation sites were visited near the source site to improve the survey for positioning of the transponder at this site, see figure 16. Table 4. Shows the result of the pinging.

Figure 15. Deployment of the transponder 1 nm east of the receiver mooring drop position.

Table 4.a Interrogation of transponders at the source location from KV Svalbard collected in September 2008.

Position (N)	(E)	Time	11.0 kHz	11.5 kHz	12.0 kHz	12.5 kHz
Site KS 1						
78,31.36229	08,18.50837	12:41:40	2.6187	1.0941	4.2654	4.1965
78,31.35268	08,18.37352	12:43:11	1.5311	2.7585	1.3468	1.0738
78,31.34942	08,18.24620	12:45:11	2.5372	1.4659	1.9721	4.0946
78,31.34955	08,18.18774	12:46:14	2.5174	2.7443	2.9074	4.0696
78,31.35167	08,18.13184	12:47:21	2.4971	2.7429	1.9296	4.0480
78,31.35257	08,18.06432	12:48:30	2.4770	2.7430	4.1536	4.0255
Site KS 2						
78,29.96959	08,18.66935	13:09:02	3.8722	1.2617	2.6517	3.9681
78,29.59910	08,18.72303	13:10:35	3.9101	1.8223	2.6639	3.9950
78,29.95557	08,18.76032	13:11:36	3.9278	1.2381	2.6747	4.0133
78,29.95347	08,18.82367	13:13:17	2.9186	2.5219	2.6939	4.0401
78,29.95401	08,18.86603	13:14:30	3.9610	2.5265	2.7073	4.0564
78,29.95512	08,18.89666	13:15:35	1.5619	2.5273	1.7718	4.0696
Site KS 3						
78,30.02700	08,11.17997	13:35:30	1.4844	4.3047	2.9056	2.6121
78,30.03926	08,11.13934	13:36:24	4.0047	4.3150	2.9210	2.6019
78,30.05413	08,11.09501	13:37:28	3.9944	4.3243	2.9400	2.5903

Table 4. b

Interrogation of transponders at the receiver location from KV Svalbard collected in September 2008.

Position (N)	(E)	Time	11.0 kHz	11.5 kHz	12.0 kHz	12.5 kHz
78,25.47900	02,31.70240	09:13:24	1.1009	1.9122	1.0112	1.0001
78,25.51595	02,31.67981	09:16:00	4.4652	2.1449	4.1980	1.0737
78,25.54341	02,31.64713	09:16:48	4.4186	2.3033	5.5678	2.7838
78,25.56123	02,31.63434	09:19:00	1.8230	2.4201	3.7076	4.7954
78,25.58206	02,31.62590	09:20:50	4.3597	2.6350	1.1903	6.0634
78,25.60661	02,31.62103	09:21:39	4.3227	2.6625	nan	nan
78,26.63012	02,28.11430	10:36:20	7.9289	4.5289	6.3437	5.2708
78,26.65513	02,28.27820	10:38:04	3.0885	4.5534	6.4359	5.3607
78,26.66792	02,28.36863	10:39:14	3.0916	4.5656	6.4835	5.4109

78,26.68022	02,28.43597	10:40:17	2.8060	4.5785	2.4725	5.4558
78,26.69594	02,28.50204	10:41:39	1.3621	4.5989	3.7667	2.4769
78,26.71423	02,28.55189	10:42:54	2.9213	4.6202	1.8199	5.5409
78,26.46330	02,23.23376	11:08:38	3.9436	5.7460	5.7257	3.9301
78,26.48069	02,23.30918	11:10:03	3.9185	5.7385	5.7612	3.9647
78,26.49450	02,23.34545	11:11:00	3.8991	5.7434	4.8721	3.7187
78,26.51098	02,23.37491	11:12:01	1.8995	5.7511	1.2602	2.4683
78,26.52979	02,23.59411	11:13:08	3.5951	1.3142	5.8932	1.4415
78,26.54750	02,23.40293	11:14:12	3.8808	5.7838	3.2813	2.7677
78,25.67908	02,21.46145	11:30:30	5.0964	2.8474	4.4737	3.2064
78,25.71019	02,21.57969	11:31:44	5.0208	5.8983	7.4110	3.2102
78,25.73320	02,21.66542	11:32:41	4.9653	5.8703	4.5205	3.2143
78,25.75834	02,21.74914	11:33:42	4.9105	5.8438	4.5517	3.2185
78,25.77768	02,21.82540	11:34:26	4.8384	4.1773	4.5784	3.2257
78,25.79914	02,21.91293	11:35:42	4.8094	5.7961	4.6070	3.1306
78,24.71400	02,24.18759	11:55:55	5.9993	5.2047	3.4135	4,2365
78,24.74228	02,24.26538	11:57:07	5.9247	6.1510	3.4183	4.1995
78,24.76629	02,24.36265	11:58:19	5.8534	5.0958	3.4219	4.1712
78,24.78222	02,24.43448	11:59:16	5.8016	5.0549	3.4246	4.1537
78,24.79347	02,24.50299	12:00:11	5.7566	3.1159	3.4292	3.9376
78,24.80612	02,24.56715	12:01:14	5.7095	2.7204	3.4360	4.1330
78,24.93764	02,30.35311	12:18:09	2.8020	3.4237	4.6804	5.8050
78,24.95911	02,30.42653	12:19:33	5.1584	3.3927	2.4644	5.8152
78,24.97551	02,30.49083	12:20:51	5.1124	3.3661	4.4719	5.8263
78,24.99745	02,30.56854	12:22:34	5.1880	3.3388	2.8476	4.6940
78,25.02055	02,30.62922	12:24:02	4.2715	3.3115	4.8160	5.8479
78,25.03981	02,30.67276	12:25:13	2.5853	3.2905	4.5249	5.8532
78,25.74381	02,27.08657	13:10:41	3.7376	3.8334	4.6071	4.2887
78,25.76111	02,27.12281	13:12:00	3.7361	2.7978	4.6437	4.3050
78,25.78096	02,27.14555	13:13:13	3.5920	3.8318	2.1114	1.8666
78,25.79223	02,27.17320	13:14:10	3.1466	2.9873	2.7941	4.3254
78,25.80877	02,27.19944	13:15:16	3.6610	3.8322	3.3853	4.3388
78,25.82204	02,27.21856	13:16:11	1.8323	3.8348	4.4323	7.1273

Figure 16. Map of the transponders drop positions and the positioning survey sites around the receiver mooring is shown in the upper plot. This survey was done during the KV Svalbard cruise. The lower plot shows the transponder drop positions and the positioning survey sites around the source mooring. The survey at the source location was partly done during the RV Håkon Mosby cruise in August and the KV Svalbard cruise. Green spots marks the ping position and the red crosses are the drop positions.

Task 4. Recovery of glider and winch mooring.

Seaglider recovery

On September 24, 2008 the Seaglider SG127 was recovered at the position $78^{\circ}44.01'N$, $006^{\circ}25.13'E$ after accomplishing the 67-day long mission in the eastern and central Fram Strait. Altogether 394 dives were performed, providing downcast and upcast profiles of pressure, temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen and light transmission for each dive. The maximum depth of diving was 1000m in deep waters. The SG127 was operated from the glider base station at Optimare in Bremerhaven. During each surfacing of the glider, the full set of measured values and engineering data was sent by the Iridium link to the base station.

Three days before recovery, the SG127 was commanded to patrol on a short distance between 006° and $006^{\circ}30'E$, performing only shallow dives down to 300 m. When the ship was already next to the last reported SG position, two hours before recovery, the glider was commanded to stop the mission and stay on the surface. Then a position of the glider was updated and reported to the ship every 5 minutes. The ship navigated to the glider position (within a safe distance) and the antenna was spotted directly from the bridge, approx. 100 m at the front of the ship. Weather was favorable for the recovery, with NW wind 15-20 knots and sea 1-2 m. Because it is particularly difficult to recover the glider from a ship with the high freeboard, the motorboat was launched to pick up the vehicle from the water. It was lifted into the boat by two people by hand (without using a frame). On board the glider was visually checked, communication with the PC terminal was established and the device was put into the travel mode. The antenna and stabilizers were disassembled for a freight.

Figure 17. Seaglider track (red dots) during the mission from July 19 to September 24, 2008 and the position of recovery by KV Svalbard. The recovery position of the profiling mooring is indicated by green dot.

Figure 18. Recovery of the Seaglider using the motorboat on September 24, 2008

Recovery of the profiling mooring

After recovery of the glider, the bottom mooring equipped with a profiling winch and CTD profiler was recovered at the position 78°49'N, 006°E. The profiling mooring was deployed in July 2008 during PS cruise ARKXXIII/2. The underwater winch with 300m cable, the electronic module to steer the winch, four battery packs and buoyancy floats, manufactured by NGK Ltd., Japan, was deployed on the top of the mooring. The mooring was additionally equipped with the steel floatation below the winch (200 kg buoyancy) and a pack of six smaller floats (25 kg buoyancy) above the releaser. Due to a failure of the CTD profiler directly before deployment, the replacement was built of four CTD sensors (MicroCats SBE37) and assembled of the frame with two buoyancy floats. The Microcats were programmed to measure with 20 s interval, giving only 2 months period of measurements. Thus the recovery, originally scheduled for 2009, had to be completed in September 2008 from KV Svalbard.

Recovery took place in a favorable weather (on the same day as the glider recovery), the mooring releaser was interrogated acoustically and after receiving the range, the release command was send. The steel floatation and the winch surfaced after releasing the anchor (ca 2-3 min later). Two motorboats were launched, one to fasten the loop and hook to the chain between the floatation and the winch, another to secure the floating Dynema cable against entangling into the ship's propeller. After the ship took position upwind to the surfaced mooring, the loop was fastened to the crane and the winch together with the steel float were lifted on the deck. After disassembling the upper part, 2500 m of the cable were pulled on the ship's winch and finally the releaser with the pack of floats was recovered. The whole recovery took ca 2.5 hours, mostly spent on hauling the cable, and was done in a secure and efficient way.

Unfortunately, the profiling top (four MicroCats) and the whole length of cable were missing from the profiling winch. This failure was the most likely due to a failure of the winch steering mechanism and too weak fixation of the cable to the winch's drum by manufacturer. The winch drum indicated also traces of corrosion. The whole mechanism will be carefully inspected after a freight of the winch to Bremerhaven and NGK Ltd. will be notified respectively.

Figure 19. Recovery of the profiling mooring from KV Svalbard September 24, 2008

Task 5. UPMC: Recovery of MOPS mooring

Conditions on site on 22/09/08

Wind NNW 30 knts , Tair -5°C

Small drifting ice floes , 3/10 concentration

Good visibility, no swell due to ice edge proximity.

Recovery sequence:

1200 : arriving on position 80°36.06N 007° 15.7E

Ship's sonar gives a good echo of the top buoys at 80m depth, at the exact GPS position.

1215 : tender boat lowered to water with 2 crews and Olaf on board

1230 : sent interrogation with TT301, reply OK, distance 700m

1235 : sent release command , distance 740m

1240 : sighting the orange buoys on surface among pack ice, argos signal received on deck receiver;

The tender boat hooks the chain between the buoys and tries to tow the mooring towards the ship. No success (too much drag) so KV Svalbard moves slowly to the boat.

1325 : after several attempts, the buoys are hooked to the crane's hook

1330 : buoys and argos beacon at deck level

1335 : mooring wire and buoys are secured on deck

1340 : crane hook is free and equipped with snatch block. Hauling out the 500m wire starts, using the starboard hydraulic winch

1408 : MOP float appears at surface at the lower end of the wire , immediately followed by ADCP and acoustic release.

1410 : all instruments are lifted at deck level , the crane is rotated to bring them above deck but the wire rips off a capstan, inducing a hard knock in the line

1412: MOP float only holds to the wire by its safety ropes (the main plastic brackets are broken) but we can bring it on deck

1412 : all instruments are safe on deck, all in good shape at first sight.

Then 2 hours were needed to remove the metallic wire from deck winch and wind it on our wooden roll.

Figure 20. The MOPS mooring was deployed from RV Håkon Mosby 2007 at 80° 36.06N 007°15.7 E at a water depth 745 m.

Some photos illustrating the recovery facilities onboard KV Svalbard

KV Svalbard appears as a suitable ship for mooring operations :

- manoeuvrability is good , due to the azimuth thrusters. Ship's rolling could become a problem for operations in heavy weather.

- the tender boats are great , powerful and easy to launch in any(?) sea state, largely due to the crews' skills. They do ease the first catch of the mooring's top part;
- The aft crane (12t at 12m) with telescopic arm is a good alternative to A-Frame; keeping it in line with the hull (ie as we did for AWI mooring), it allows a safe recovery over the ship's stern.
- Hydraulic winches (one on each side) are OK to wind the wires, though a bit slow .

We only recovered moorings, but almost certainly a deployment would be possible in similar conditions . Last but not least , the coast guards are really great , helpful and friendly folks to work with.

Figure 21. The Aft deck onboard KV Svalbard.

Figure 22. The Hydraulic winch used for mooring line.

Figure 23. Photos showing the small boat operations for mooring recovery within partly ice-covered area.

Figure 24. Photos which show the recovery of the MOPS – DAMOCLES mooring.

Summary of results.

During the cruise it was confirmed that the source is transmitting according to the pre-programmed schedule! We have listen to the source at 22 stations at different ranges from the source inside ice edge, outside ice edge and at the 500 m depth contour east of the source near Forlandet. Acoustic recording was carried out using the short hydrophone array attached to a 150 m long cable hanging out from the small boat “Sjøbjørn” 1-2 nm away from a relatively silent KV Svalbard. At some locations the source signal is very clear on other locations more carefully analysis are needed to determine if the source signal can be detected at that particular location.

We got 16 XTs down to 480 m along the 130 km long section between source and receiver. A mini CTD was brought to provide additional stations at the other listening stations. However, the CTD was lost at the first attempt of taking CTDs from the ship at the receiver position. The mini CTD came under the ship and into the propellers during ship manoeuvring. KV Svalbard divers tried to save the

CTD, but failed to get it before it went off the thin line. Correspondingly the oceanographic information during the rest of the cruise is missing. This is not first time CTDs are lost during use from KV Svalbard. Crew on board KV Svalbard said that they will look into how they can provide a more safe way to do CTD from the ship.

The fourth transponder was successfully deployed 1 nm in easterly direction from the receiver mooring drop position. Transponders at the receiver mooring were pinged at 7 different sites. At each of the ping sites 5-6 pings were made. Pinging was done from KV Svalbard. At the last day of the cruise an additional survey was carried out around the source mooring. This survey consisted of four different ping sites.

The acoustic modem was tested several times from the small boat "Sjøbjørn". The modems replied, but they do not yet work perfect with regard to data download. Only very limited data was downloaded. Aquatec will look into the result of downloaded data and debug files. The failure of downloading acoustic data with the modem will cause delays for the inversion and assimilation of acoustic data. However, the acoustic measurements obtained by the "hand-hold" hydrophone sausage reduced the effect of this lack of data, and will make us more prepared to analyze the data when the moorings are recovered next year.

Two oceanographic moorings, one 680 m long MOPS mooring and one 2500 m long mooring with a winch on top was successfully recovered. The MOPS mooring was recovered in partly ice covered region, while the winch mooring was recovered in open water. The recovery of the moorings took 2-3 hours each, and in both occasions the small boats was used. Everything went fine during recovery, but the four micro CATs owned by AWI was not recovered with the winch mooring. These items fall off the mooring long time before the recovery operation started. Based on this experience we are planning to deploy the tomography moorings from KV Svalbard next summer within the ACOBAR project. Furthermore, the seaglider was steered to position from base at Optimare, Germany, located from the bridge of KV Svalbard, and successfully caught and brought up by use of "Sjøbjørn" within 30 minutes.

Three small ice stations were visited. Ice stations were taken in combination with acoustic listening activities using Sjøbjørn. Ice floes were covered with a half-meter thick layer of hard fresh water ice. This made it difficult and time consuming to drill holes for ice thickness measurements. AWIs EM sledge was used on two ice stations.

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